

Comparison Between NorSand Cambridge Type and SaniSand Type Models in Simulating Sand Behavior under Monotonic Loading

Seyyed Kazem Razavi^{1,2}, Samuel Yniesta², Alireza Yaseri³, & Khashayar Nikoonejad⁴

¹ BGC Engineering INC. Vancouver, BC, Canada

² Department of Civil, Geological, and Mining Engineering, Polytechnique Montreal, Montreal, QC, Canada

³ Department of Civil Engineering at the Royal Military College of Canada

⁴ International Visiting Graduate Student, University of Toronto, ON, Canada

ABSTRACT

NorSand Cambridge type models employ a single yield surface plasticity with an associated flow rule, whereas SaniSand type models are formulated using bounding surface plasticity with a non-associated flow rule. Despite their distinct formulations, their approaches to simulating the monotonic behavior of sand rely on similar concepts. Both models measure the distance from the current stress condition to a specific moving target toward critical state in the stress space to calculate their hardening behavior. This paper presents how these entirely different frameworks share this similar concept in simulating the monotonic behavior of sand and shows a comparison of their modeling abilities.

RÉSUMÉ

Les modèles NorSand de type Cambridge utilisent une unique surface de plasticité avec une règle d'écoulement associée, tandis que les modèles de type SaniSand sont formulés en utilisant une surface limite et une règle d'écoulement non-associée. Bien que leurs formulations diffèrent, leurs approches pour modéliser le comportement monotonique des sables se reposent sur des concepts similaires. Les deux types de modèles mesurent une distance entre les conditions actuelles de contraintes, et un état de contrainte cible qui se déplace vers l'état critique dans l'espace des contraintes, afin de calculer le comportement d'érouissage. Cet article présente comment ces cadres conceptuels partagent ce concept similaire pour la simulation du comportement monotonique des sables, et montre une comparaison des capacités de modélisations des modèles.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the field, soils undergo undrained and drained shear loading along different stress paths. By opposition, specific mechanical responses of soil can be observed under controlled stress paths using various laboratory devices like compression triaxial, extension triaxial, and hollow cylinder tests. These responses can form normalized patterns that can be used to construct constitutive soil models. The more normalized patterns incorporated into these models, the higher their capability and accuracy in simulating arbitrary stress paths observed in the field. Notably, the development of NorSand type and SANISand type models has considered features such as critical state, phase transformation stress ratio, stress-dilatancy rule, and peak state observed in mechanical behavior of dense samples.

This paper aims to demonstrate how these two types of models incorporated these patterns into their formulations. It explains the reasons behind their similar simulation results under certain conditions and their divergent responses in other situations. In this study, the Dafalias and Manzari (2004) model (DM2004) and the modified NorSand model (MNS2015) by Jefferies et al. 2015, a modification of the original NorSand model by Jefferies (1993), are used to investigate the behavior of both types of models.

In this paper, all confining stresses are effective, and compressive stress and reduction in volume are considered positive. The formulation is given for triaxial conditions with the following definitions:

$$p = \frac{\sigma_1 + 2\sigma_3}{3}; \quad q = \sigma_1 - \sigma_3; \quad \eta = \frac{q}{p} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_1 + 2\varepsilon_3; \quad \varepsilon_q = \frac{2}{3}(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3); \quad D = d\varepsilon_v^p / d\varepsilon_q^p \quad (2)$$

where p is the mean effective stress, q is the deviatoric shear stress, and η is the stress ratio. Deviatoric and volumetric strain are denoted ε_q and ε_v , respectively. σ_1 and σ_3 are the major and minor effective principal stresses, while ε_1 and ε_3 are major and minor principal strains. The superscripts e and p are used to distinguish between the elastic and plastic parts of the strain, respectively. D is plastic dilatancy.

2 KEY SOIL RESPONSES CONSIDERED BY BOTH MODELS

2.1 Critical State

The critical state is the final state that the soil experiences upon further shearing at large deviatoric strains (ε_q). Roscoe et al. (1958) defines it as a state where the soil continues to deform in shear under constant mean effective stress (p), constant deviatoric stress (q), and constant void ratio (e). Mathematically, the critical state can be expressed with the following conditions:

$$\varepsilon_q \rightarrow \infty \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial q}{\partial \varepsilon_q} = \frac{\partial p}{\partial \varepsilon_q} = \frac{\partial e}{\partial \varepsilon_q} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Therefore, in the (e, q, p) space, critical state is a point for a given stress path. For different initial states, the final

state could differ, and all these final points form the critical state line expressed by the following equation.

$$C(e, q, p) = 0 \quad (4)$$

The three-dimensional shape of the CSL in (e, q, p) space can be mapped on the (e, p) and (q, p) space. For granular soils, the critical state line in (e, p) space can be fitted by the following equation (Li and Wang, 1998):

$$e_c = a + b \left(\frac{p}{p_{ref}} \right)^c \quad (5)$$

where, a , b , and c are material constants. The CSL in (q, p) space is a line passing through the origin that follows the equation:

$$q = M \cdot p \quad (6)$$

where, M is the slope of CSL in (q, p) space.

2.2 State Parameter

Been and Jefferies (1985) introduced the state parameter (ψ) to quantify how far from the critical state the current state of density (identified by p and e) is. A positive value indicates that the soil current state is looser than the critical state, while a negative value indicates that the soil state is denser than the critical state. The state parameter is defined as the distance between the current state and the critical state in terms of void ratio using Equation (7).

$$\psi = e - e_c \quad (7)$$

where e is the current soil's void ratio at a given mean effective stress (p), and e_c is the critical state void ratio at the same mean effective stress. The state parameter changes during loading because of the changes in void ratio and mean effective stress due to contraction and dilation.

2.3 Peak State of Dense Samples

Figure 1 shows the typical mechanical response of a dense sample undergoing drained triaxial compression loading. From the figure, the sample shows a peak deviatoric shear strength followed by strain softening prior to reaching critical state (peak point 2 in the figure). All related quantities at this state are denoted with the subscript "b", referring to the bounding state. As a result, M_b , p_b , ψ_b , and D_b correspond to the peak stress ratio, mean effective stress, state parameter, and plastic dilatancy at the bounding state. It should be noted that Jefferies (1993) uses $\eta_{max} = M_b$, $D_b = D_{min}$, and $\psi_b = \psi_{min}$ for its notations.

MNS2015 uses the following relationship between different quantities at peak point (bounding state):

$$D_b = \frac{M - M_b}{1 + N \cdot \text{sign}(\psi_b)} \quad (8)$$

where N is called shear-volume coupling factor.

Figure 1 Concept of bounding state as understood from typical drained tests on dense samples (Modified after Razavi and Yniesta, 2024)

Equation (8) is referred to as Nova's rule and was proposed by Nova and Wood (1985) for dense samples with negative ψ_b . However, for positive ψ_b the equation changes to be used in the NorSand model using $sign(\psi_b)$ in Equation (8). Jefferies (1993) also proposed the following relationship between plastic dilatancy and state parameter at bounding state.

$$D_b = \chi_{tc}\psi_b \quad (9)$$

This relationship is known as state-dilatancy rule, where χ_{tc} is called state-dilatancy parameter. By combining Equation (8) and (9), the relationship between M_b and ψ_b as used by MNS2015 can be obtained.

$$M_b = M - \chi_{tc}\psi_b(1 + N \cdot sign(\psi_b)) \quad (10)$$

DM2004 uses the following relationship between M_b and ψ_b in its formulations:

$$M_b = M \exp(-n_b\psi_b) \quad (11)$$

where n_b is a material constant.

2.4 Phase Transformation Stress Ratio

Phase transformation is a temporary state where a transition from contraction to dilation occurs in sands having negative state parameters. This feature shows itself by a change of direction in the undrained stress path, which occurs when the mean effective stress shifts from a reduction to an increase. In the (q, p) space, by drawing a line between the origin and the phase transformation point, a line is formed called the phase transformation line (PTL). The slope of PTL is called the phase transformation stress ratio (PTS). M_i and M_d are the symbols used for phase transformation stress ratio in MNS2015 and DM2004 model respectively. The PTS varies with the state parameter, with denser sands exhibiting lower PTS values. Each model uses its defined PTL relation with state parameter as follows:

MNS2015:

$$M_i = M - N\chi_i|\psi_i| \quad (12)$$

ψ_i represents the image state parameter corresponding to the mean effective stress at the image state. The image state is a point on the NorSand model's yield surface that corresponds to zero dilatancy. χ_i is called NorSand state-dilatancy parameter and is obtained using the following formulation (as noted by Razavi and Yniesta, 2024):

$$\chi_i = \frac{\chi_{tc}}{1 - \lambda \frac{\chi_{tc}}{M_i}} = \frac{\chi_{tc}}{1 - c \cdot b \left(\frac{p_i}{p_{ref}} \right)^c \frac{\chi_{tc}}{M_i}} = \frac{\chi_{tc}}{1 - c(a-e) \frac{\chi_{tc}}{M_i}} \quad (13)$$

In χ_i formulation, M_i is evident on the left side. Substituting this equation into Equation (12) reveals that M_i needs to be solved for.

$$M_i = M - N \frac{\chi_{tc}}{1 - \frac{\chi_{tc}}{M_i} c(a-e)\chi_{tc}} |\psi_i| \quad (14)$$

The constraints arise from solving this equation, and an alternative method for defining the phase transformation stress ratio using a nonlinear state dilatancy law (instead of Equation 9) was suggested by Razavi and Yniesta (2024). However, since the paper is focused on MNS2015, for simplicity and to avoid potential numerical instability when solving Equations (14), M_i can be substituted by M on the left side. With this assumption, M_i is obtained as follows for the NorSand model in this paper:

$$M_i = M - N \frac{\chi_{tc}}{1 - \frac{\chi_{tc}}{M} c(a-e)\chi_{tc}} |\psi_i| \quad (15)$$

DM2004:

This model simply uses the following relationship between M_d and ψ in its formulations:

$$M_d = M \exp(n_d\psi) \quad (16)$$

where n_d is a material constant.

Figure 2 shows how the bounding stress ratio and the phase transformation stress ratio change with the state parameter in NorSand and SANISand. Both models aim to match these changes for dense states (negative ψ_b) using their specific material constants. As seen in Figure 2, both models must follow similar trends for dense samples. However, for loose samples (positive state parameters), the models show different trends according to Equations (10), (11), (15), and (16). The reasons for these differences will be explained in the Section 4.

2.5 Stress-Dilatancy Rule

Dilatancy evolves during shear loading, reaching zero at critical state. The dilatancy can be related to the soil mobilized stress ratio (η). The relationship between the mobilized stress ratio and dilatancy is called the stress-dilatancy rule. This relationship is valid for the entire stress - strain history, and therefore, the behavior of the soil is controlled through it. Using PTS, the stress-dilatancy rule can be defined as follows:

MNS2015:

$$D = M_i - \eta \quad (17)$$

DM2004:

$$D = A_d(M_d - \eta) \quad (18)$$

where A_d is a constant used by DM2004. Equation (17) and Equation (18) suggest that whenever $\eta = M_i$ in MNS2015 or $\eta = M_d$ in DM2004, dilatancy should be zero a feature that must hold true due to the definition of phase transformation considered in previous section.

Stress-dilatancy rule also can be explained through plastic work dissipation rate (\dot{W}^p), which is defined as follows:

$$\dot{W}^p = p \cdot d\epsilon_v^p + q \cdot d\epsilon_q^p \quad (19)$$

Figure 2 Variation of a) bounding stress ratio, and b) phase transformation stress ratio with state parameter used by SANISand and NorSand model

By dividing by the mean effective stress and the plastic shear strain increment the following equation is obtained, where the dilatancy and mobilized stress ratio are related to each other:

$$\frac{W^p}{p d\epsilon_q^p} = \frac{d\epsilon_v^p}{d\epsilon_q^p} + \frac{q}{p} = D + \eta \quad (20)$$

where the following equations are obtained by comparing Equation (20) with Equation (17) and Equation (18):

$$\text{MNS2015} \quad D = \frac{\dot{W}^p}{p d\epsilon_q^p} - \eta = M_i - \eta \quad (21)$$

$$\text{DM2004} \quad D = \frac{\dot{W}^p}{p d\epsilon_q^p} - \eta = A_d(M_d - \eta) \quad (22)$$

3 MNS2015 AND DM2004 FORMUALTIONS

3.1 Elasticity

For comparing two models' performance, let's assume both models use the same equations for their elastic bulk and shear modulus:

$$G = G_0 \frac{p_{ref}}{e - e_{min}} \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_{ref}}\right)^{0.5}, \quad K = \frac{2(1+\nu)}{3(1-2\nu)} \quad (23)$$

here, G_0 and e_{min} are material constants, and p_{ref} is the reference pressure. ν is the Poisson's ratio.

3.2 MNS2015

MNS2015 is an associated flow rule model, meaning that the plastic strain rate's direction is normal to the yield surface, allowing to formulate the subsequent function based on this assumption:

$$D = -\frac{dq}{dp} \quad (24)$$

By utilizing Equation (19) and Equation (15) and performing integration, the yield surface of MNS2015 can be derived as follows.

$$f = \eta - M_i \left(1 - \ln\left(\frac{p}{p_i}\right)\right) = 0 \quad (25)$$

MNS2015's yield surface takes a bullet-type shape, similar in shape to the yield surface of the original Cam-Clay model (Figure 3a). The point on the yield surface that exhibits zero dilatancy is referred to as the image state, which is characterized by three parameters: image stress ratio (M_i), image confining pressure (p_i), and image state parameter (ψ_i).

Figure 3 Concept of the critical, dilatancy, and bounding state in q, p space used by (a) NorSand and (b) SANISand

M_i and p_i control the dimensions and position of the yield surface within the stress space. As defined in Equation (15), M_i depends on ψ_i , and considering that ψ_i is a function of p_i , any alteration in p_i will ultimately impact the size of the yield surface. In MNS2015, p_i is assumed to change with the plastic deviatoric shear strain in the following manner:

$$\frac{dp_i}{p} = H_{NS} \cdot d\varepsilon_q^p + \frac{S}{p} \frac{\eta}{M_b} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{p_i}{p_b} \right)}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_q^p \quad (26)$$

where H_{NS} is the plastic modulus. The second term on the right side of the equation is known as the cap-softening term, which can be activated or deactivated through the switch S . By setting $S = 0$, this cap-softening term is deactivated. In this paper, we have deactivated this term because the model without cap-softening has close features to DM2004. To see the effect of cap-softening on the model's performance, readers are encouraged to read the work by Razavi and Yniesta (2023).

Jefferies (1993) introduced the following plastic modulus for the NorSand model:

$$H_{NS} = \left(\frac{p}{p_i} \right) (H_0 - H_y \psi) \left(\frac{p_i}{p_b} - \frac{p_i}{p} \right) \quad (27)$$

H_0 and H_y are NorSand's hardening parameters. H_{NS} compares the mean effective stress at bounding state with the current mean effective stress to determine whether an expansion or shrinkage should occur. Whenever $p > p_b$, the yield surface will expand; otherwise, it will shrink.

3.3 DM2004

DM2004 is a non-associated flow rule model. As a result, it should have a yield surface and potential surface. DM2004's yield surface is defined as below:

$$f = |\eta - \alpha| - m = 0 \quad (28)$$

The yield surface of DM2004 forms a wedge in the q - p space, as depicted in Figure 3b. This wedge is governed by two parameters, m and α . Parameter m determines the opening of the wedge, typically set to 0.05, while parameter α adjusts the slope of the bisecting line of the wedge. When stress conditions lie within the shaded area, the behavior is elastic.

Plasticity occurs when the stress conditions are on the edge of the wedge and attempt to exceed it. In these conditions, the flow rule follows Equation (18), and the slope of α changes according to the following equation:

$$d\alpha = d\eta = H_{DM} \cdot d\varepsilon_q^p \quad (29)$$

where H_{DM} is the plastic modulus, obtained using the following equation:

$$H_{DM} = G_0 \frac{h_0(1-c_h e)}{|\eta - \eta_{in}|} \left(\frac{p}{p_{ref}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (M_b - \eta) \quad (30)$$

η_{in} represents the initial stress ratio at the beginning of the simulation. h_0 and c_h are hardening constants controlling the rate of change of stress ratio with deviatoric shear strain.

3.4 Material Constants Used by Both Models for Toyoura Sand

This paper will compare the performance of MNS2015 and DM2004 using triaxial test data for Toyoura Sand found in the literature (Verdugo and Ishihara, 1996). Material constants used by both models are shown in Table 1. For DM2004, this data is sourced from Dafalias and Manzari (2004) to maintain consistency with prior literature. The parameters χ_{tc} and N for NorSand have been chosen to make NorSand's M_i and M_b to align with the variations of M_d and M_b observed in SANISand for dense states, as shown in Figure 2. The hardening parameters of NorSand were determined through a trial-and-error method to achieve the best fit with both the simulation and measured data.

Table 1 Material constants used by SANISand and NorSand models to simulate the monotonic behavior of Toyoura Sand

	MNS2015	DM2004
Elastic modulus		$G_0 = 125$
		$e_{min} = 0.62$
		$\nu = 0.05$
Critical state		$M = 1.25$
		$a = 0.934$
		$b = 0.019$
		$c = 0.7$
Bounding and phase transformation stress ratio	$\chi_{tc} = 5$	$n_b = 1.1$
	$N = 0.7$	$n_d = 3.5$
		$A_d = 0.704$
Hardening rule	$H_0 = 100$	$h_0 = 7.05$
	$H_y = 500$	$c_h = 0.968$
Yield Surface	-	$\eta_{in} = 0$
		$m = 0.01$

4 PERFORMANCE OF THE MODELS TO SIMULATE THE MONOTONIC BEHAVIOUR OF GRANULAR MATERIALS

Comparing Equation (27) and Equation (30) shows that the plastic modulus used in both models exhibits similarities. Both models compare the bounding state (p_b in NorSand, and M_b in SANISand) with the current state (p in NorSand and η in SANISand) to determine the hardening-softening (or expansion-shrinkage) behavior of their respective yield surfaces shown in Figure 3. As long as $p > p_b$ or $\eta < M_b$ the controlling parameter of yield surface evolution will rise; otherwise, it will reduce. However, since their yield surfaces are completely different, the rule of bounding state varies significantly between both models. In the NorSand model, the bounding state controls the peak deviatoric shear strength. While, in SANISand, the bounding surface governs the evolution of stress ratio.

For example, during an undrained test of a loose sample, the stress ratio consistently increases until it reaches the critical state (refer to Figure 4), while the sample experiences peak deviatoric shear strength followed by a strain softening before reaching the critical state (this behaviour is known as flow liquefaction). Consequently, in

NorSand, there needs to be a transition in the hardening regime from hardening to softening for the model to simulate this feature. In contrast, for SANISand, the stress ratio should continually increase, and there should be no alteration in the hardening behavior of the model.

In other words, NorSand's hardening rule has been designed to control deviatoric stress evolution with strain, while SANISand's hardening rule has been designed to control stress ratio evolution with strain. Since the role of bounding state differs for loose samples under undrained loading conditions, they should exhibit different trends for their bounding state with state parameter. This is the reason why in Figure 2a, NorSand's bounding state does not fit SANISand's bounding state. NorSand tries to use lower bounding state to better capture the peak deviatoric strength under undrained loading for loose samples.

Figure 4 Schematic view of typical undrained triaxial behavior of loose samples: a) in $q - p$ space, b) in q - deviatoric strain and in η - deviatoric strains

Under drained tri-axial loading conditions for dense samples (as depicted in Figure 5), both models exhibit strain softening in terms of deviatoric stress and stress ratio at the same point. This indicates that the bounding state for samples in a dense state should be the same for both models, as illustrated in Figure 2a.

Therefore, for both models, the concept of the bounding state remains consistent for dense states but differs significantly in meaning and application for loose samples. In NorSand, the bounding state for loose samples aligns with the stress ratio at which flow liquefaction initiates (instability point). However, in SANISand, identifying the stress ratio corresponding to flow liquefaction initiation is not straightforward. Andrade et al. (2013) attempted to

locate this point for DM2004 in the $q - p$ space by setting dq/dp equal to zero under undrained loading condition.

Figure 5 Schematic view of typical drained triaxial behavior of dense samples: a) in $q - p$ space, b) in q - deviatoric strain and in η - deviatoric strains

In Figure 6, the measured data for stress ratio versus the corresponding state parameter at the instability point for loose samples under undrained triaxial compression loading is shown for Toyoura Sand. The bounding state used by NorSand (taken from Figure 2a on the loose side) is also presented in the same figure for comparison. It is evident that the measured trend is inconsistent with what NorSand utilizes. For samples with lower state parameters, NorSand will predict a higher instability stress ratio (resulting in higher undrained peak deviatoric strength). Conversely, samples with higher state parameters (looser samples) will exhibit a lower instability stress ratio (corresponding to lower peak deviatoric strength).

Figure 7 displays the simulation results for Toyoura Sand subjected to undrained loading using SANISand. The void ratio for all samples is 0.907, while initial confining pressure changes range from 0.1 to 2 MPa. As it can be seen, SANISand has been successful in simulating the non-flow behaviour of a dense sample with $p_0 = 0.1MPa$ and flow behaviour of loose samples with $p_0 = 1MPa$ and $p_0 = 2 MPa$.

Figure 6 Measured undrained instability stress ratio versus corresponding state parameter for loose samples of Toyoura Sand with NorSand bounding state concept (Data extracted from Verdugo and Ishihara, 1996)

Figure 7 Simulation results versus measurements using SANISand for Toyoura sand with $e_0 = 0.907$ (Data extracted from Verdugo and Ishihara, 1996)

The simulation results obtained using the SANISand model with DM2004 can be used as a baseline for comparing with NorSand. In Figure 8, a comparison is presented using simulation results for the same samples with $e_0 = 0.907$ and varying values of p_0 : 0.1, 1, 2, and 3 MPa. From the

figure, both models provide good simulation results for the dense sample with $p_0 = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, exhibiting non-flow behavior. However, as the loose samples are simulated with an increase in p_0 from 1 MPa to 3 MPa, differences become apparent. For loose samples with $p_0 = 1 \text{ MPa}$, and $p_0 = 2 \text{ MPa}$, NorSand exhibits higher peak deviatoric stress compared to SANISand. However, as the sample becomes looser at $p_0 = 3 \text{ MPa}$, a reversal occurs, and NorSand shows lower deviatoric peak strength.

Figure 8 Simulation results using NorSand and SANISand for Toyoura sand with $e_0 = 0.907$

Several researchers have proposed different methods to improve NorSand's applicability for properly simulating static liquefaction in loose samples:

- Jefferies et al. (2015) proposed adding a cap-softening term to the model's original hardening rule, as shown in Equation (26).
- Razavi (2023) and Razavi and Yniesta (2024) have suggested using another formulation for the bounding state of loose samples, introducing a new material property. In this definition, the bounding state should be seen as instability state for loose samples.
- Razavi and Yniesta (2024) have proposed making NorSand's hardening rule dependent on stress ratio. With this newly developed hardening rule, the model's performance regarding static liquefaction can be enhanced.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a comparison was made regarding the formulation of NorSand and SANISand, highlighting their similarities and differences. The NorSand version introduced by Jeffries et al. (2015), known as MNS2015, and the SANISand version introduced by Dafalias and Manzari (2004), named DM2004, were utilized for the comparison.

Both models incorporate a term called "bounding state" in their hardening rules. This term detects changes in the yield surface by comparing the current state with the bounding state for each model. The study revealed that the concept of bounding state is the same for dense samples in both models. However, for loose samples, there is a significant difference in concept and definition. In NorSand, the bounding state for loose samples corresponds to the instability state occurring during flow liquefaction. In SANISand, the bounding state controls the evolution of stress ratio with deviatoric strain, and its concept remains consistent for both loose and dense samples.

The linear function used for NorSand's bounding state with the state parameter for loose samples does not perfectly align with the measured instability state that occurs in loose samples. Specifically, for loose samples with lower state parameters, it generally produces higher deviatoric peak strength, while for highly loose samples, it produces lower deviatoric peak strength.

To better simulate static liquefaction using NorSand, the model needs to consider one of the following approaches:

- Activate the cap-softening term.
- Consider different functions or different material parameters controlling for the bounding state for loose and dense samples.
- Change its hardening rule completely to make it a stress-ratio dependent hardening rule.

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